

**URBAN
LAND USE
FACTSHEET**

EU MISSION 'A SOIL DEAL FOR EUROPE'

Healthy soils are essential to life on Earth. They are the foundation of our food systems, they also provide clean water and habitats for biodiversity while contributing to climate resilience. Yet, between 60% and 70% of soils in the EU are considered unhealthy. While it can take hundreds of years to form just one centimetre of soil, it can be lost in a single rainstorm or through industrial damage.

The EC launched the Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe' - Horizon Europe programme - **to create 100 living labs and lighthouses** in rural and urban areas to drive the transition to healthy soils by 2030.

Funded by the European Union

THE MISSION SOIL WILL¹:

- > Create knowledge and solutions for soil health,
- > Advance the development of a harmonised framework for soil monitoring in Europe,
- > Increase people's awareness of the vital importance of soils,
- > Support the EU's ambition to lead on global commitments, notably the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and contribute to the European Green Deal targets.*

¹ European Commission

[*more information in the Mission implementation plan.](#)

THE 8 MISSION OBJECTIVES

1

Reduce desertification

2

Conserve soil organic carbon stocks

3

Stop soil sealing & increase re-use of urban soils

4

Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration

5

Prevent erosion

6

Improve soil structure to enhance soil biodiversity

7

Reduce the EU global footprint on soils

8

Improve soil literacy in society

THE MISSION SOIL LIVING LABS ARE...

“user-centred, place-based and transdisciplinary research and innovation ecosystems, which involve land managers, scientists and other relevant partners in systemic research and codesign, testing, monitoring, and evaluation of solutions, in real-life settings, to improve their effectiveness for soil health and accelerate adoption.” Factsheet - EU Mission Soil Deal for Europe: Living labs and lighthouses.

CHALLENGES IN URBAN LAND USE

The main challenges of Urban Mission Living Labs can be identified and synthesised as follows:

First, to prevent hazards (e.g. presence of toxic and harmful elements) to reduce pollution and improve structure and biodiversity of urban soils (objectives 4,6).

Second, to mitigate negative externalities (e.g. pollution, contaminations, emission) to conserve soil organic stocks, stop sealing and reduce global footprint (objectives 2, 3, 7).

Third, to incentivise transformations to enhance restoration through infill reclamation, regeneration, remediation, reuse, upcycle plans and projects (objective 3).

Fourth, to reduce the urban heat island effect, through reducing sealing and increasing soil organic carbon stocks.

Fifth, to improve communication and literacy on urban soils (objective 8).

A key priority is tackling soil sealing — the permanent covering of soil by impermeable materials — which reduces ecosystem services, worsens pollution, and contributes to the urban heat island effect.

WHY IT'S A PROBLEM

- Less soil = biodiversity loss
- Urban heat rise
- More flooding risk
- Increased commuting from expansion

LIVING LAB SOLUTIONS

- Boosts urban biodiversity
- Protects suburban agriculture
- Encourages walkability & local access
- More natural space near people
- Reduced transport costs

THE QUADRUPLE HELIX TYPES OF STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED IN LIVING LABS

An essential feature of Living Labs is their user-centric approach, involving all key actors and end-users throughout the innovation process. While specific participants vary by context, they can be grouped using the **Quadruple Helix Model**—Academia, Industry, Government, and Civil Society—forming a **Public-Private-People Partnership (PPPP)** that enables real co-creation and impact.

This inclusive model supports co-learning and ensures that solutions are not only scientifically sound but also practical, economically viable, socially accepted, and environmentally sustainable.

SOME EXAMPLES OF STAKEHOLDERS OF LIVING LABS IN THE URBAN LAND USE MAY INCLUDE:

- **GOVERNMENT:** Public authorities and Private agencies, Public administrations (e.g. local, county-regional, national, communitarian), Health authorities (e.g. public health, epidemiologists), Environmental managers (e.g. disaster/risk and environmental managers); Maintenance (e.g. Planners and managers of public infrastructure).
- **INDUSTRY:** Building/construction professionals (e.g. civil engineers, architects, real estate), GIS specialists, and Urban Planners (e.g. landscape, transport).
- **CITIZENS, CIVIL SOCIETY & USERS:** Inhabitants (e.g. residents, tenants), Civic groups (e.g. associations, cooperatives, NGOs), Loosely organised groups (e.g. artists, designers, retailers, and local businesses), and more informal interest groups of the communities.
- **ACADEMIA:** Universities and Research institutions - social sciences (e.g. anthropologists, economists, planners, geographers, sociologists), physical sciences (e.g. agronomists, biologists, chemists, climatologists, geologists, epidemiologists, physicians).

WHICH ADDED VALUE CAN CO-CREATION BRING IN THIS FIELD?

Reconcile different stakeholders' types and interests around one agenda of soil health actions.

Activate a series of co-design activities supporting soil health, while increasing land stewardship, sense of belonging and overall urban resilience to climate change.

Establish co-monitoring communities towards a pro-active role of citizens on soil issues in cities.

Settle a shared governance model on urban Mission Soil Living Lab to be followed in cities for upscaling and further co-creation pathways.

WHICH ACTIVITIES CAN AN URBAN MISSION SOIL LIVING LAB PERFORM?

They would be the platforms where different expertise can meet and collaborate to support policy decisions and interventions (e.g. identifying and monitoring the presence of toxic and harmful elements; or identifying risks for heat island or flooding and codesigning solutions).

They would bridge concrete stakes of urban users with practical solutions of different types of professionals, also in a cross-sectoral perspective.

They would create the occasions to grasp emerging demands on land use interventions, guiding both formal and informal practices.

They would support and enhance communication activities, organising thematic seminars, meetings, focus groups with professionals and the population.

Only tight cooperation between public companies, citizens, industry and local government can lead to a successful mutually connected system, which optimises resources and economic, environmental, and social results. This is a long-term project of transformation towards a different society, which ensures developmentally focused management of resources in local and regional areas.

ANDREJ FIŠTRAVEC, MAYOR OF MARIBOR

CRITERIA TO IDENTIFY

LIVING LABS*

Aims

- **Innovation, co-creation**, formal learning
- Contribution to **societal challenges**
- **Improving soil health and related ecosystem services** (= > mission objectives)

Participants

Public-private people partnership:

- **Real soil managers** (farmers, advisors, foresters, city greens managers, allotment holders, etc.) to be at the centre of the innovation process.
- **Other stakeholders:** Associations and organisations with an interest in soil health, local or regional government, scientists from a variety of fields outside of soil (natural sciences, social and behavioural sciences), and the wider public.

Activities

- **Co-creation, co-development & experimentation** of innovations improving soil health and related ecosystems
- **Research on impact of these innovative practices on ecosystems**
- **Networking** and **knowledge exchange**
- **Demonstration** (in particular lighthouses)

Context

- Multiple **disciplines** (-> transdisciplinary, inc. social sciences), **methods**, dimensions (technical, economic, social)
- **Place-based** approach and **real-life context** = real farms/forest/urban sites
- **Robust scientific setup** for **ecosystem assessment**
- **Openness**, communication, dissemination

*adapted from McPhee et al. (2021)

LIGHTHOUSES

As lighthouses are sites achieving exemplary performance in terms of soil health improvement, the criteria for selecting them will be based on the **mission objectives**, indicators, and thresholds as defined by the monitoring programme:

- **Demonstration, dissemination, and promotion** to soil managers, the public, and the policy arena, at the landscape scale and beyond, of land-use systems that satisfy criteria for sustainable development, in particular in terms of soil health and related ecosystem services.
- Reaching out to the **policy arena** linking results of the Lighthouses to environmental rules and regulations. This is in line with science-based policy support and governance.

HOW TO PARTICIPATE? TWO LIVING LAB TOPICS

1) **Brownfield**

HORIZON-MISS-2025-05-SOIL-01: Living Labs for soil remediation and green redevelopment of **brownfields**

- **Single-stage** submission
- **Deadline:** 30 September 2025
- 4-5 Living Labs for each application - should be located in at least three different Member States and/or Associated Countries

2) **Biogeographical regions**

HORIZON-MISS-2025-05-SOIL-01-two-stage: Living labs to enhance soil health in **Continental, Boreal and Alpine biogeographical regions**

- **Two-stage** submission (First, applicants submit a brief outline. Selected proposals are then invited to submit a full application)
- **Deadline:** 4 September 2025 (first stage) and 18 February 2026 (second stage).
- 4-5 Living Labs for each application - **Most of the living labs** (i.e., 3 out of 4, or 4 out of 5) must be located **within the chosen region**

Research and Innovation Actions:

100% funding for any actor
Proposals must apply the multi-actor approach
Support to third parties is allowed

WANT TO EXPLORE FURTHER?

Biogeographical Regions factsheet

Both Living Lab topics on the SOILL website

HOW TO GET INVOLVED IN THE SOIL MISSION

FOLLOW THE SOILL PROJECT!

Check out
for updates

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SOILL HUB

A collaborative space
dedicated to soil health.

HELPDESK

A wide network of experts
ready to provide guidance and
answers on many topics.

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